

SMART4ENV Project: Enhancing the Scientific Capacity of TUBITAK MAM in the Field of Smart Environmental Technologies For Climate Change Challenges

Selda Hocaoglu¹, Burcu Kiran^{1*}, Sebnem Aynur¹, Fatone, F.², Salas, S.P.³, Maletsky, Z.⁴, Piccinetti, L⁵.

¹TUBITAK Marmara Research Center (TUBITAK MAM) (Speaker)

²Università Politecnica delle Marche (UNIVPM)

³Fundacio Universitaria Balmes (UVIC-UCC)

⁴Norges Miljo-Og Biovitenskaplige Universitet (NMBU)

⁵Sustainable Innovation Technology Services Limited (SITES)

Abstract

The EU Green Deal Strategy defined tackling climate and environmental-related challenges as “this generation’s” defining task. Digital solutions have the power to deliver substantial environmental gains through increased efficiencies and have increasingly been deployed in improving environmental sustainability. One of the key areas the European Council encourages the Commission to act in are digital solutions for climate mitigation. Digital technologies offer hardware, software, and equipment infrastructure to enable more connected, intelligent, efficient, and responsive systems and services. All this translates into concrete benefits for environmental resources management utilities. SMART4ENV Project aims to improve capacities for stimulating scientific excellence in key applications of Smart Environmental Solutions (SES) for the mitigation and adaptation to climate change of economies while strengthening consortium’s scientific reputation, attractiveness and networking channels. At scientific level, it is expected to enlarge the community of competitive prestigious researchers in SES, stronger and better-connected to a core of international and relevant R&I systems, supported by skilled R&I managers with their international networks. At social level, it is expected an improvement in environmental quality, public health, improved customer experience and communication, a better mitigation and adaptation to climate change because of new SES for intelligent, connected, and responsive environmental services and a sustainable use of water and resilient treatment systems with stable effluents quality. At an economic level, the project will contribute to the development of an innovative SES industry and the profitability of regional companies through new product development, process improvements, innovation support, and job creation.

The project strategy is based on building a sustainable framework for research capacity, step up excellence and active international networking. First pillar assesses current capacity while analysing

capabilities to gain experience and competence for achieving targeted aims. Then, based on the gap analysis, actions will be determined by considering Turkiye's national priorities and a roadmap will be established, which will evolve throughout the project. In the second pillar, sustainability actions will be carried out to improve viable institutional networking and collaboration. The third pillar includes a continuous outreach and stakeholder-oriented events following the implementation of Project communication and dissemination strategy. The research part is composed of 6 case studies. The case studies will favour innovative solution finding and transferring know-how, lessons learnt and best practices through networking activities while developing capacity building and dissemination.

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Contacts: burcu.uyusur@tubitak.gov.tr (+90 262 677 2919), selda.murat@tubitak.gov.tr,
sebnem.aynur@tubitak.gov.tr, f.fatone@staff.univpm.it, sergio.ponsa@uvic.cat,
zakhar.maletskyi@nmbu.no, leonardo@sinnovations.org

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